

VALIAS - Valorization of Marine Invasive Alien Species a Pathway Towards the Protection of European Marine Biodiversity: From Destructive Invaders to a Source of Wealth

Deliverable D1.2.
Title: Data Management Plan

Project

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1. Introduction

The VALIAS project as an international multidisciplinary consortium aims to pioneer a responsible and integrated approach to control the population of Invasive Alien Species (IAS) in European seas, during a period when interactions with economic sectors as well as other natural resources users multiply rapidly across the globe. Therefore, the main goal of this project is to bridge the growing gap between resource scarcity and the demands of a growing population, within the scope of European initiatives. VALIAS consortium with the presence of academic and non-academic partners from Greece, Cyprus, Italy, Ireland and Bulgaria aims to build a strategy for the control of marine European IAS population through sustainable valorization pathways of this underexploited biomass feedstock:

- Develop new valorization pathways of IAS creating new strategies towards their population management and preservation of European marine biodiversity
- Create a new, and more importantly, sustainable source of natural safe and stable ingredients that can be integrated at an industrial level within the food, feed and cosmeceutical supply chain
- Cover the consumers' demand for chemical free, natural and sustainable products
- Empowering and improve the productivity of European fisheries, aquaculture, food and cosmetic sector with environmental, economic and social acceptance

The VALIAS Data Management Plan (DMP) is part of Work Package 1 and adheres to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data management principles and the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot) approaches. Developed in accordance with the Open Access & Data Management Guide, this document represents the first version of the DMP, delivered in the sixth month of the project. The DMP aims to provide an overview of the datasets that VALIAS will generate, alongside guidelines for the collection, analysis, storage, dissemination, and overall management of research data throughout and beyond the project's duration. This DMP is intended to be a dynamic document, evolving over the course of the project to incorporate new datasets, methodologies, and policies.

2. Data summary

Data within VALIAS is generated via literature review and existing databases on selected invasive alien species (sIAS) and experimental studies.

The following data will be collected and/or produced within VALIAS project:

1. Literature review on aspects of distribution, biology, ecology, toxicity and processing of the species of interest (task 3.2). This data will derive from scientific publications and the grey literature, online databases, citizen scientists, other projects. It will be used to produce D3.2 which is an excel file on the distribution of sIAS.
2. The evaluated results from Task 5.3 concerning use of novel ingredients and performance of novel aquafeeds for sea bream will be shared according to the common treatment agreed among all partners of VALIAS project. Concerning data collection methods for key performance indices, measurements will be performed at regular intervals for weight and length, and sampling procedures to collect tissue and blood samples for health status will also be a method for summarising data.
3. Experimental data

It is expected that data being produced within the VALIAS project is essentially new data as it is based on novel methods, and technologies, that will lead to new products valorizing sIAS. VALIAS partners will share data in order to commonly address the needs of the project's outcomes. Moreover, some of the data may be of interest for other scientists' groups to use them as well as the industry (e.g. aquacultures, cosmetics, pharmacology). The latter is subject of this data management plan and further referred to as VALIAS Open Access Data.

3. FAIR data

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The research data and the publications from the VALIAS project will be deposited on the Zenodo platform (<https://www.zenodo.org/>), which is an EU-supported portal for big data management and extended digital library capabilities for open access and open data. More specifically, the research data and publications will be deposited on the Zenodo-curated OpenAIRE platform (<https://www.openaire.eu/>), which is the major EC-supported initiative for fostering open science in Europe. All VALIAS Open Access Data will be made accessible by a unique digital object identifier. Research data deposited on Zenodo is assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number, being a unique and persistent identifier. This will ensure the tracing and referencing the data.

The VALIAS Project hosts its own Zenodo Community and Repository where all data will be uploaded and accessible via the following link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/valias>.

In order to make data easier to find and re-use, keywords (including the project acronym -VALIAS) will be provided. Other keywords might include (non-exhaustive list): invasive alien species (and the species' name when necessary), keywords relatable to the project's scope (e.g. cosmetics, pharmaceutical, toxins/toxicity, aquafeeds, encapsulation). Finally, version numbers will be provided, when and if applicable.

3.2 Making data accessible

The provision of open access data is the responsibility of the relevant partners. Many of the partners have their own institutional data repositories with their own procedures and rules for access. Whether the data will be made fully open immediately will be decided case-by-case. In any case, all data will be made fully accessible after publication of the corresponding article. In addition, data from platforms and previous projects, have their own data usage and accessibility restrictions that will be fully followed. If partners have no own repository, they may either use public repositories, such as for example the Zenodo repository, or repositories of other VALIAS partners.

The data will be shared securely among internal partners while the external sharing and accessibility will be performed via peer-reviewed journals and conference presentations.

Should any patents or new products will be produced, then an embargo period will be applied, for at least 12 months after the conclusion of the project.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Within VALIAS project, data and metadata produced is fully interoperable as it will be provided in standard excel, word and/or pdf files. Thus, even with minimum computer skills, anyone could have easy access and use the data. In addition, Zenodo follows DataCite Metadata Schema (<https://schema.datacite.org/>), the latter being a list of core metadata properties chosen for an accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes, along with recommended use instructions. All the above, make VALIAS data and metadata fully interoperable.

No project-specific ontologies or vocabulary will be generated.

3.4 Increase data re-use

As stated in the previous sections, all data will be, unless otherwise required, free to use. Scientific publications and/or conference presentations of the outcomes will be sought, and this will allow for a possibly widest re-use of the research output. In addition, as the research data and metadata of VALIAS project will be deposited on Zenodo for open access, they will be freely available and their re-use will be encouraged. Finally, with respect to scientific publications, the data will remain reusable without any specified time, and as far as Zenodo is concerned, the policy is that items deposited on the platform will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.

Data quality assurance will be in line with the principles of research integrity and responsible research.

4. Allocation of resources

All VALIAS data and metadata will be stored in repositories bound to the FAIR principles. Costs incurring for publishing in open access journals, would be the responsibility of the partner responsible for the corresponding publication. Zenodo publishing is free of charge, as it is a free online repository. The responsibility for data management is with the individual principal investigators of the research groups where the data has been produced. No further costs related to preservation of the data beyond the funding period are required.

5. Data security

All data is securely stored on two ways: the computers (preferably with a back up in an external hard drive) of each of the partners responsible for their production and a project-specific Google drive. Produced data and metadata will be deposited to Zenodo, ensuring their long-term preservation and curation. No personal data will be stored with VALIAS Open Access Data sets.

6. Ethics

Project VALIAS will be managed in compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law in the implementation of research and innovation activities. Any ethical concerns raised by those activities will be handled following rigorously the recommendations provided in the European Commission Ethics Self-Assessment Guidelines. Concerning all procedures involving experimental fish will be in compliance to the

EU ethical guidelines on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes (Directive 2010/63/EU).

7. Other issues

The project does not make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management.